

Gujarat Government Initiative MDM Program on Poverty Alleviation and Child Education Development

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strengths and weaknesses. Where the MDM program operates is stratified according to literacy levels and development criteria.

The investigators chose vadodara in the chhotaudepur district of central Gujarat, one of the most backward arid regions with a low level of culture and was selected for research, entitled "Comparative Study of Lunch Effectiveness" on the Primary School Education in Gujarat. "And collect data from central Gujarat.

Object of study :-

1. To study the Gujarat government initiative MDM program on poverty alleviation and child education development.
2. To reviewed to explore health linkages that assess beneficiary perceptions and to identify beneficiary health and education-related improvements.

MDMS management in Gujarat

The structure of the MDMS flows from the Stale Level to the district level and then to the taluka. The Committee (MDM) is supported by the Joint Commissioner and two State Assistant Commissioners. The Collector / City Commissioner is responsible at the district level and is assisted by a deputy collector / Mamlatdar and three support staff - Agent Mamlatdar (Executive), Deputy Mamlatdar (Check) and

ABSTRACT

Educational play a vital role in the development of human potential. The state government uses a significant portion of its limited resources to provide educational facilities throughout the country. Due to the socio-economic factors that exist in society, the goal of these efforts to stimulate the percentage of universal education in general seems to be far-reaching and elusive. Most children from low socioeconomic societies suffer from undernutrition, often dropping out of school at an early age, directly affecting their personality development. Several scenarios have been initiated to address these issues

Keywords: Child Education, MDM Program

INTRODUCTION

The noon meal plan is one of the earliest supplementary nutrition programs in the country. The program has nutrition and education goals. It began in 1984 as part of the Gujarat Applied Nutrition Program for school-age children, 6-11 years old, as a reward program for all primary school children. Coverage has gradually increased to high school children.

Each beneficiary's plan is expected to receive 330 calories and 7 to 12 grams of protein supplements. The central and state governments are considering a phased expansion of the noon meal plan to replace food buffer stocks, taking into account the government's emphasis on primary education. It is necessary to evaluate existing plans to understand their

Deputy Mamlatdar (Account) team. Taluka Mamlatdar, like Taluka level, is responsible for the head of the program. At school level, organizers, chefs and assistants are assigned to lunch and distribute. The School Management Committee expects to monitor the overall performance of the program.

Problems facing Gujarat

The Plan Approval Committee of the Noon Meal Plan met on April 17, 2014 to review the implementation and progress of the Gujarat Midday Lunch (MDM) program. The report highlights various issues related to the implementation of MDMS, such as: 28% of enrollment rates for primary school programs are not covered. Monthly data entry on MIS portals in Ahemdabad, Dangs and Vadodara

Point out that it is poor. Against the approval of the 2013-14 14th Cook cum Helper, 1364 Cook cum assistants were not hired. In all schools, feed supply per child is incompatible, resulting in uneven distribution of food. 17.78% of boys and 9.83% of girls are malnourished. Most children taking part in school do not take advantage of MDM. One common problem is that MDM is harmful to health because it is not prepared for healthier situations.

The situation of Indian children is best described as a permanent humanitarian emergency. Hunger and under nutrition can undermine your child's health. Today,

according to recent orders from the Supreme Court, every child who has attended a public school is entitled to a nutritious meal. However, this right is far from being realized: the coverage of lunch is close to universal, but the quality of most states is still very low. Various implementation issues have arisen in the states where lunch has begun. Occasionally there have been reports of food poisoning, especially in Pondicherry, where hundreds of children have recently fallen ill after eating noon milk.

Teachers complain that a meal at noon will encroach on their time or disrupt their classroom habits.⁸ Another example comes from Delhi, where the Delhi High Court instructed 126 students to pay 400,000 rupees in January 2004 as compensation. Government school food.

Many studies have reported on the improper implementation of lunch. They suggested the importance of the role of the teacher at lunchtime. But teachers' opinions and experiences on lunch are completely different. Some teachers said that lunch time has greatly increased their workload.

They are expected to retain records of food and funds. Some teachers are satisfied with the operation of the lunch in the school. They reported that the lunch ended "classroom hunger" and now the children are more focused. It directly improves their academic performance.

Some teachers like to eat dry food during freshly prepared lunches. They think it is easier to check the quantity and quality of food given to children. A principal is very opposed to the plan. He felt that there was no need to provide lunch when the authorities were unable to provide adequate drinking water at the school. The teachers also reported that the lunch led to the interruption of the course. They complain that the vision and smell of cooking food distracts the children.

On the other hand, the teacher should "taste" the food in front of the children, check that there are no outdated ingredients, and whether the meal is healthy (rice and salt will not do). The teacher should also supervise the child's hand washing, and in the process can also see the child's nails and general hygiene. The actual service and consumption of the meal should be supervised by the teacher for orderly and hygienic conduct. Chinese food can also be used by teachers as a variety of educational activities; educate children about good living habits and teach some nutrition education.

The universally applicable noon meal plan currently covers nearly 12 children across the country, making it the largest school feeding program in the world. However, issues related to dietary quality continue to attract attention and new monitoring and surveillance methods are needed. In some cases, teachers were found to be exhausted, and then they were unable to attend classes in the afternoon (Orissa). In some states, teachers are forced to participate in a lunch program, although the state government prohibits teachers from participating in any activity other than learning. It has also been found that some teachers are not aware of the goals of the lunch program.

The study also found that some teachers believe that lunch will affect teaching and learning. Therefore, efforts must be made to make teachers aware of the advantages of providing meals in schools as a means of improving the nutritional status of children. It is therefore clear that teachers can play an important role during lunch time.

Therefore, in order for lunch to become a complete universal program, teachers must be properly positioned at lunchtime. Every Indian child should actually get a free, delicious and nutritious lunch. Therefore, research on the lunch plan for teachers is very important.

Research methods are critical in the research process. It describes the various steps taken to plan and addresses research issues such as how the problem is developed, definition of terms, choice of survey topics, validation of data collection tools, data collection analysis and interpretation, and process inference and generalization.

Teachers cannot prove that they teach and evaluate their children's professions in these schools. In addition, a senior teacher said that the quality of education will definitely be affected. Students pass the exam whether or not they have studied. This will make them affected in later life, when there are competitive exams and medical or engineering entrance exams.

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